

Protonation Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of 3-Bromo-2-Hydroxy-5-Methylacetophenone, Its Oxime and *n*-Propylimine

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Potentiometric studies have been carried out on 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone, its oxime and *n*-propylimine in dioxane-water (20 to 75%, v/v) media at different ionic strengths 0.02*M*, 0.05*M* and 0.1*M* (NaClO₄) and temperatures 25, 30 and 35°. The thermodynamic parameters viz. Δ*G*, Δ*H* and Δ*S* were evaluated.

THE complexing properties of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and their Schiff bases derived from hydroxylamine and primary amines are of much interest. These ligands have been found to be useful reagents for the estimation of transition metals^{1,2}. In the present communication, the protonation constants of 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone (BMHA), 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenoneoxime (BMHAO) and 3-bromo-2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone-*n*-propylimine (BMHA-*n*Pr) have been studied in dioxane-water media at different ionic strengths and temperatures by using Calvin-Bjerrum technique³.

Experimental

Synthesis of ligands: A 50% acetic acid solution of 2-OH, 5-Me-acetophenone⁴ was brominated in ice-bath to form 3-Br, 2-OH, 5-Me-acetophenone (BMHA). The BMHA on condensation⁴ with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and *n*-propylamine gave BMHAO and BMHA-*n*Pr.

Materials: The reagents used were all BDH-grade. Pure distilled water was redistilled over alkaline KMnO₄. The dioxane was purified⁴.

Apparatus: I. T. L. pH-meter model M-110 was used for pH measurements. The electrode assembly consisted of glass and calomel electrodes dipped in the titration mixture. The pH meter was calibrated at pH=4.05 and 9.15 with aqueous potassium hydrogenphthalate and borax buffer respectively.

Potentiometric studies: The following solutions were titrated against standard carbonate free (0.52*M*) sodium hydroxide⁵ solution. The total volume was kept 40 ml with 75% v/v dioxane content.

- (i) (0.02*M*) HClO₄ + (0.08*M*) NaClO₄.
- (ii) (0.02*M*) HClO₄ + (0.08*M*) NaClO₄ + (0.004*M*) ligand.

The ionic strengths, $\mu=0.1M$, 0.05*M* and 0.02*M* were maintained by the addition of appropriate quantities of sodium perchlorate solution. The titrations were carried out in 20-75%(v/v) dioxane-water media maintaining the temperature at 30° ± 1 with the help of a thermostat. The titrations were also carried out at temperatures 25, 30 and 35° and ionic strength $\mu=0.1M$.

Calculations: The average number of protons ($\bar{n}_A$) associated with ligands was determined from the acid and ligand titration curves employing the equation of Irving and Rossotti⁶. The calculations of protonation constants were carried out by plotting a graph between $\bar{n}_A$ vs pH. The log K_1^H values have been obtained at half integral value. The values were also obtained by the equation 1:

$$\log K_1^H = pH + \log \bar{n}_A / (1 - \bar{n}_A) \quad \dots (1)$$

The values obtained by the two different methods were in good agreement. The average values of log K_1^H are reported in Table I.

TABLE I—Log K_1^H VALUES FOR BMHA, BMHAO AND BMHA-*n*Pr AT 30°

Ligands	Dioxane-water%(v/v)				Ionic strength(<i>M</i>)		
	$\mu=0.1M$				Dioxane-water(v/v)75%		
	20	40	60	75	0.05	0.02	0.00
BMHA	8.75	9.80	10.05	10.86	11.05	11.18	11.45
BMHAO	8.25	8.82	9.51	10.12	10.22	10.42	10.70
BMHA- <i>n</i> Pr	8.51	9.05	9.82	10.36	10.52	10.70	10.96

Discussions

The log K_1^H value (11.85) of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone (HA) was obtained in 75% dioxane-water medium at 30 ± 1° and ionic strength $\mu=0.1M$ (NaClO₄) by Kamat and Dator⁷. In the present case the log K_1^H value for BMHA is 10.86 indicating the enhanced acid strength. The lower value of log K_1^H for BMHA can be ascribed to the strong electron withdrawing nature of the bromine atom situated

at *ortho* position with respect to the phenolic -OH. The electron releasing effect of the methyl group present at position-5, though should reduce the acid strength of BMHA, is not much significant due to enlarged distance over which it has to operate. The intramolecular hydrogen bonding between hydrogen of phenolic -OH and oxygen of >C=O group which may lower the acid strength of BMHA, is also not very effective. The -I effect exerted by bromine dominates.

It is interesting to note the effect of the presence of the azomethin group (>C=N-) in place of the keto group. The keto-oxime (BMHAO) and the keto-imine (BMHA-nPr) are found to be more acidic than the ketone (BMHA) as is evident by their lower log K₁^H values 10.16 and 10.36 respectively. This may be due to the presence of O-H...N bond which is weaker than O-H...O bond present in the ketone BMHA. The release of phenolic hydrogen in keto-oxime and keto-imine will be promoted. Further it has also been observed that the keto-oxime (BMHAO) is more acidic than the keto-imine (BMHA-nPr). This may be due to the possibility of hydrogen bond formation by oxygen of phenolic group and hydrogen of oximino group which imparts additional stability to anion derived from the oxime (BMHAO)

Effect of dioxane content : The dielectric constant of the medium decreases with increase in dioxane percentage⁹. It has been observed that log K₁^H values for all the compounds under consideration increase with increase in dioxane percentage indicating the fall in acid strength of the compounds. The electrostatic force between the ions increases with decrease in dielectric constant thus facilitating the formation of molecular species by suppressing the ionization, resulting in an increase in log K₁^H values⁹. The variation of log K₁^H values with dioxane percentage is depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

Effect of ionic strength : No change in the shape of formation curves drawn at different ionic strengths was observed. This suggests that the various species co-exist in the solution. The interaction of ions decreases with increase in μ-values of the medium as log K₁^H values are found

to decrease. From the graph between log K₁^H vs √μ, as depicted in Fig. 2, the protonation constants at zero ionic strength were obtained by extrapolation of the values of log K₁^H to zero ionic strength. The values are reported in Table 1.

Fig. 2

Effect of temperature : The log K₁^H values at temperatures 25, 30 and 35° have been recorded in Table 2. The thermodynamic parameters viz. ΔG, ΔH and ΔS have been calculated from equations 2, 3 and 4 respectively. The values are recorded in Table 2.

$$\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta H = 2.303R \frac{T_2 \times T_1}{T_2 - T_1} \log \frac{K''}{K'} \quad (3)$$

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T} \quad \dots (4)$$

It is concluded that with the change in temperature there was no appreciable change in the values of protonation constants and thus temperature has no significant effect on the acid strengths of these ligands. The negative values of ΔH indicate that the protonations of the ligands are accompanied by liberation of heat and the process is exothermic¹⁰. The high positive values of ΔS indicate that the protonations of the ligands tend to proceed spontaneously¹¹.

TABLE 2—PROTONATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS FOR BMHA, BMHAO AND BMHA-nPr AT μ=0.1M(NaClO₄) IN 75%(v/v) DIOXANE-WATER MEDIUM

Ligands	Temperature °C	log K ₁ ^H	-ΔG K. cal./mole	-ΔH K. cal./mole	ΔS cal./deg./mole
BMHA	25	10.92	15.10		
	30	10.86	14.98	5.08	32.8
	35	10.80	14.90		
BMHAO	25	10.17	14.21		
	30	10.12	14.04	4.04	32.6
	35	10.08	13.82		
BMHA-nPr	25	10.42	14.52		
	30	10.36	14.36	4.46	32.7
	35	10.32	14.22		

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